

Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System

Jose Eduardo D. Jamir¹, Stephen V. Posadas¹, Riyaldo F. Tablac¹, Alvin Jason A. Virata²,
William A. Aldea III²

¹Information Technology Department, St. Dominic College of Asia

²School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of Asia

jedjamir@sdca.edu.ph, svposadas@sdca.edu.ph, rftablac@sdca.edu.ph, ajavirata@sdca.edu.ph,
waaldea@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Most different schools are using free existing hotel management system in practicing basic hotel front desk operations and one of the most important skills that the Hospitality and Tourism Management (HTM) students should have is the knowledge of using the front desk facilities. Through this study, the proponents develop and improve the use of existing hotel management system of the School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management Department into the Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System in order to help the instructors on teaching basic operations skills for hotel business management and also for students to visualize the hotel front desk facilities and equipment for the said department. The conceptual framework of the system was designed for making it user-friendly for the user to have a better output of the system. As for the result of the study, the usability of the system meets the user's requirements based on the overall mean which is highly acceptable. Also, for the efficiency of the system, the users will be more productive and efficient using the system. The findings clearly suggested that the proposed system should be available in a mobile application and reform the hotel management front desk simulation system into online web-based system.

Keywords: *Hotel management, Front Desk, Simulation.*

Introduction

Today, simulations are frequently used tools, not just as analytical tools to support decision-making, but also as instructional tools in management education. This case shows how a subject based on a computer simulation has progressed from being regarded as a "waste of time" by most stakeholders to being a model by which other subjects are measured. The case would explain how a specific simulation is utilized, as well as why a simulation cannot be taken "off the shelf" and turned into the tool it can be, but rather requires a continuous process of lecturer and student review and improvement (Edelheim & Ueda, 2007).

The Hotel Management System has been designed to simplifying the task of bookings, managing inventory, availability date and rates, and process of transactions such as payments, refunds and cancelation of bookings. The Hospitality and Tourism Management (HTM) students must have learned the basic skills and should have the knowledge and capabilities in basic operations of using the system. The existing system is fixed, so that is why it cannot be customized, and it is not a user-friendly system which makes very hard for the students to learn easily. Also, there is no security of data gathered in the existing system that will cause the system very vulnerable. This study focused on developing and implementing the system to provide the customers and clients a unique, innovative and easy-to-use interface that improves the way people use the web today.

Hotel Management System is a web-based hotel management system, which includes, guest management, booking management, day rate management, availability booking calendar, invoices, and receipts and reports. The Hotel Management System is required to provide the following features to the user(s): easy access to information for both administration and registered personnel, reduced administrative costs, clear payment date information, and keeping track of all hotel rooms and guests. The data should be accurate, consistent, dependable, and comprehensive (O'Fallon & Rutherford, 2010).

The Online Hotel Reservations System is a platform for faculty members to teach their students the fundamentals of hotel reservation. Each account had to have a username and password issued to it for security purposes. The creation of student and client accounts was managed and supervised by a system administrator (Delizo & Esguerra, 2013)

This system is a new generation of hotel software that comes with a list of features that help you maximize your sales and marketing, rooms, food and beverage, finance, and general services operations. For instance, Folio Plus is a task automation solution that caters to the needs of hospitality personnel and supervisors on a regular basis. Room reservations, room allocations, guest check-ins and check-outs, and other front-desk tasks are among the aspects of hotel management operations (Jinisys Software, n.d.).

The Administrator has full access to the system page and will be able to amend all customer records for bookings made via website booking or walk-in customers, modify the status of customer reservations, and update the list of hotel services. The administrator would also enable generating reports containing information about the reservations made as well as the overall revenue received (Adap et al., 2013).

The Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System would benefit the students by providing a faster way of educating them about managing a hotel. This will save time and effort of the students. The administrator will be notified by the system through the notification function. There will be a notification if there is an update on booking. The researchers wanted to improve the environment inside the system. The researchers decided to create a dynamic system that will help them explore client's knowledge in Hotel Management like Housekeeping Management, Room Management, Administration Management, and Booking Management. The Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System is also a great help teaching the process of managing a hotel. This system is part of the educational process of the students to know the basics of doing front-desk management. The system is not only responsible for doing reservations; but it is also responsible for design customization of different pages for students to learn how to design their hotel. The system aims to give complete service that the students need.

Methodology

System Paradigm

Figure 1 Agile methodology by Beck et al. (2001)

System Development Approach

The proponents used the agile model as the basis of the SIHTM proposed system. Through the help of system development, the life cycle stages of System development will be defined by its phase.

The first phase is the planning stage which tackles planning, requirement specifications needed for the project development. The proponents had an interview to gather important information and requirements for the said project to have a better output.

The second phase is the design stage. The proponents design accordingly that will meet the client's requirements, making it user-friendly and easy to understand for the users.

The third phase is the implementation stage. The proponents focuses about implementing the said project. The system is developed and tested for its functionality which is referred to as unit testing.

The fourth phase is the testing stage. The proponents would conduct a system test, including the client for testing each part of the system to determine its functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability.

The last phase is the maintenance stage. In this phase, the system is maintained since the system will undergo changes once delivered to the clients. The system will be enhanced to accommodate the changes that could happen during the testing period.

Figure 2 Conceptual framework for Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System

Level of Satisfaction

This tackles about the functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability and portability of the system evaluated by the expert user and end-user.

The **functionality** refers to the range of operations that can be run on a system.

The **reliability** focuses on the ability of the system to perform tasks requested by the user.

The **usability** discusses the ability to use the system in an easier and understandable way.

The **efficiency** focuses on the effectiveness of the system to display information.

The **maintainability** focuses on the ability of the system to identify and verify the changes of the system.

The **portability** focuses on capability of the system that can be run on other platforms.

The table below shows the evaluation for each respondent to answer the question utilized by the proponents.

Table 1 Likert scale for Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System

Scale	Range	Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Highly Acceptable
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately Acceptable
3	2.51-3.50	Acceptable
2	1.51-2.50	Needs Improvement
1	1.00-1.50	Not Acceptable

Results and Discussion

Respondents' Distribution

The table below shows that the system's evaluation was conducted by 70 End-Users and nine (9) Expert-Users with a total of 79 respondents.

Table 2 Respondents' distribution for Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
End-User	70	88.61%
Expert-User	9	11.39%
Total	79	100%

Overall Level of Satisfaction

The table below shows the overall level of satisfaction based on respondents' distribution. The researchers determined the system's rating through the results of the evaluation test from the expert-users and end-users after computation.

Table 3 Overall level of satisfaction based on respondents' distribution for Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System

Category	Expert-User	End-User	Overall level of satisfaction	Rating
Functionality	4.1	4.5	4.3	Moderately Acceptable
Reliability	4.0	4.6	4.3	Moderately Acceptable
Usability	4.4	4.6	4.5	Highly Acceptable
Efficiency	4.5	4.7	4.6	Highly Acceptable
Maintainability	4.2	4.6	4.4	Moderately Acceptable
Portability	4.2	4.6	4.4	Moderately Acceptable
AVERAGE	4.2	4.6	4.4	Moderately Acceptable

For functionality, the system is “moderately acceptable” with a total mean of 4.3. The overall mean for the end user is 4.5 which is “moderately acceptable”. The overall mean for the expert user is 4.1 which is “moderately acceptable”.

For reliability, the system is “moderately acceptable” with a total mean of 4.3. The overall mean for the end user is 4.6 which is “highly acceptable”. The overall mean for the expert user is 4.0 which is “moderately acceptable”.

For usability, the system is “moderately acceptable” with a total mean of 4.5. The overall mean for the end user is 4.6 which is “highly acceptable”. The overall mean for the expert user is 4.4 which is “moderately acceptable”.

For efficiency, the system is “highly acceptable” with a total mean of 4.6. The overall mean for the end user is 4.7 which is “highly acceptable”. The overall mean for the expert user is 4.5 which is “moderately acceptable”.

For maintainability, the system is “moderately acceptable” with a total mean of 4.4. The overall mean for the end user is 4.6 which is “highly acceptable”. The total overall mean for the expert user is 4.2 which is “moderately acceptable”.

For portability, the system is “moderately acceptable” with a total mean of 4.4. The overall mean for the end user is 4.6 which is “highly acceptable”. The total overall mean for the expert user is 4.2 which is “moderately acceptable”.

Results show that the overall level of satisfaction is 4.4 which is “moderately acceptable”. This reveals that the system is effective towards the users. With that, students will be able to experience a realistic scenario for professions in hotel reservation and management thanks to the technology. It also functions as a learning tool for students, as the system will teach more information and skills on how to handle an online hotel reservation system, which is becoming increasingly popular in the hospitality industry (Delizo & Esguerra, 2013).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The researchers were able to create a web-based Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System, which supports the following; transparency of reports, generation of booking and payment process, print and downloadable PDF files of expenses, housekeeping status reports, and easy-to-manage system.

The proponents concluded that the system design has a specific user-interface module for Hotel Management Simulation System. The system was developed with all gathered relevant data requirements of the Hotel Management Simulation System. This has undergone beta testing and user-acceptability. The proponents also conducted a survey and the overall rating for the system is “Moderately Acceptable”. The system is accepted based on the interpretation of the client and the overall functionality, effectiveness, and efficiency of the web-based system that will benefit the employees, students, and the institution.

The study shows that the Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System should cater the needs of users. As the study progressed, the findings clearly suggested that the Hotel Management Front Desk Simulation System should be available in mobile applications and reform this kind of system into online-based web system.

References

- Adap, C. L. S., San Juan, J. R., & Sillo, P. B. (2013). *Online billing and reservation system for Royal Palm Paradise Resort* [Unpublished bachelor's thesis]. De La Salle University – Dasmariñas.
- Beck, K., Beedle, M., van Bennekum, A., Cockburn, A., Cunningham, W., Fowler, M., Grenning, J., Highsmith, J., Hunt, A., Jeffries, R., Kern, J., Marick, B., Martin, R. C., Mellor, S., Schwaber, K., Sutherland, J., & Thomas, D. (2001). *Manifesto for agile software development*.
https://moodle2019-20.ua.es/moodle/pluginfile.php/2213/mod_resource/content/2/agile-manifesto.pdf
- Delizo, G. A., & Esguerra, M. A. (2013). Online hotel reservation and management system for the College of International Tourism and Hospitality Management (CITHM). *International Journal of Computers & Technology*, 10(1), 1201-1229.
- Edelheim, J., & Ueda, D. (2007). Effective use of simulations in hospitality management education—a case study. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport and Tourism Education*, 6(1), 18-28.
- Jinisis Software. (n.d.). *Folio Plus Hotel Management System*. <https://jinisissoftware.com/hotel-management-system-folio-plus/>
- O'Fallon, M. J., & Rutherford, D. G. (2010). *Hotel management and operations* (5th ed.). Wiley.